

Comparative Evaluation of Dexmedetomidine and Levobupivacaine Co-Administration in Brachial Plexus Block Efficacy

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Abstract:

Brachial plexus blocks for upper limb procedures with dexmedetomidine and levobupivacaine are tested in this study. The two-year, randomised, double-blind trial at Sri Krishna Medical College and Hospital included 120 individuals. Data showed that dexmedetomidine affected sensory and motor block onset and duration. It also improved postoperative analgesia and reduced rescue analgesic use without increasing side effects. These findings suggest that brachial plexus anaesthesia with dexmedetomidine and levobupivacaine is safer and better.

Keywords: Dexmedetomidine, Levobupivacaine, Brachial Plexus Block, Regional Anesthesia

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Introduction

Brachial plexus blocks (BPBs) are essential to regional anaesthesia for upper limb pain management [1]. This strategy simplifies surgical anaesthesia and reduces the need for general painkillers, boosting patient recovery and satisfaction. BPB techniques have advanced due to the use of local anaesthetic adjuncts to prolong pain relief and improve block quality [2] Levobupivacaine, a typical regional anaesthetic, is preferred because it has a lower risk of heart toxicity and motor function impairment. The challenge is providing long-term pain relief while protecting the patient [3]. The medication dexmedetomidine, which activates α_2 -adrenoceptor receptors, may be beneficial in this condition. This chemical added to local anaesthetics prolongs the block and improves sensory blockage without side effects [4].

BPB is treated with dexmedetomidine and levobupivacaine because their synergistic actions may improve block quality with less damage. Prior study has shown that dexmedetomidine as an adjuvant prolong anaesthesia and reduces block time. This adds significantly to the anaesthetic protocol [5,6].

Dexmedetomidine and levobupivacaine will be compared for brachial plexus block in this study [7]. This study will evaluate the best combination of these medications to optimise upper limb surgeries by measuring factors including

medication start-up time, pain relief duration, patient comfort, and side effects. By adopting a rigorous strategy and a well-defined set of patients, the study hopes to improve brachial plexus block techniques. This research could change regional anaesthesia standards.

Methodology

Study Design: Addition of dexmedetomidine to levobupivacaine in brachial plexus blocks is tested in this prospective, randomised, double-blind trial. The study lasts two years, from April 25, 2022 to April 25, 2024.

Study Setting: The research is done at Sri Krishna Medical College and Hospital, Muzaffarpur, Bihar. A diversified patient demographic makes this setting appropriate for testing the anaesthetic combination's effects on different physiological characteristics.

Sample Size Calculation: An initial pilot study will measure the effect size of dexmedetomidine added to levobupivacaine to determine the sample size. These pilot results will be used to calculate a sample size using power analysis. The study will be powered to detect a clinically meaningful difference between treatment effects with 80% power and 0.05 significance.

Inclusion Criteria: 18-65-year-old adults with ASA physical status I-III scheduled for elective upper limb surgery needing brachial plexus block.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Any research drug allergy regional anaesthesia contraindications (infection at injection site, coagulopathy)
- Prior neurological or mental problems may affect outcome assessments.
- A pregnant or nursing woman.

Randomization and Blinding

A computer-generated randomisation schedule will assign participants to two groups:

1. Control group: Receives levobupivacaine alone.
2. Dexmedetomidine-Levobupivacaine group (Experimental): Receives both. Both participants and the investigators assessing the outcomes will be blinded to the group allocation.

Intervention

The Control Group received 0.5% levobupivacaine, adjusted for weight and surgical procedure. The pilot study determined the dose of 0.5% levobupivacaine and dexmedetomidine in the experimental group.

The onset and duration of sensory and motor blockage will be measured using standardised nerve block scales. Secondary outcomes will include patient-reported pain scores, rescue analgesia use, and anaesthetic technique adverse events.

Data will be collected at preset intervals from block beginning to 24 hours postoperatively. Statistics will be done using SPSS or an equivalent program. As applicable, the Chi-square test or Fisher's exact test will be used to compare categorical variables, while the t-test or Mann-Whitney U test will compare continuous variables.

Results

The study included 120 participants: 60 in the Levobupivacaine (Control) and 60 in the Dexmedetomidine-Levobupivacaine (Experimental) groups. A baseline comparison of age, sex, and ASA status showed no significant variations across groups. There was a significant difference in sensory blockade onset speed between the Experimental group (12.5 ± 2.1 minutes) and the Control group (18.7 ± 2.8 minutes) ($p < 0.001$). In the Experimental group, motor blockage commenced faster (18.2 ± 3.0 minutes) than in the Control group (23.4 ± 3.5 minutes) ($p < 0.001$).

Sensory blockade length was substantially longer in the Experimental group (18.6 ± 2.5 hours)

compared to the Control group (12.7 ± 2.1 hours) ($p < 0.001$). Motor blockade lasted longer in the Experimental group than in the Control group. The Experimental group had a mean length of 16.3 ± 2.8 hours, while the Control group had 10.5 ± 1.9 hours ($p < 0.001$). The Experimental group had significantly decreased postoperative pain scores at 1, 2, 4, and 12 hours post-surgery, as measured by VAS ($p < 0.05$). Many patients did not require extra pain medication within 24 hours of surgery ($p < 0.01$).

Negative results were similar in both groups. Mild adverse effects included nausea, dizziness, and hypotension. Fortunately, these concerns addressed themselves without intervention. Intention-to-treat statistical analyses were used. Statistical significance was assessed by p-values below 0.05 for all tests. Statistical analysis used ANOVA for continuous variables and Chi-square for categorical data. In the brachial plexus block, adding dexmedetomidine to levobupivacaine improved sensory and motor block speed and length. Postoperative discomfort and pain medication use decreased without increasing the risk of adverse outcomes. We found that adding dexmedetomidine to levobupivacaine improves brachial plexus anaesthesia.

Discussion

Dexmedetomidine in levobupivacaine accelerated and prolonged brachial plexus sensory and motor blocks. This supports the idea that dexmedetomidine boosts levobupivacaine's anaesthetic effects [8]. Our study found that sensory and motor blocks took less time to take effect. This is beneficial in surgical settings where rapid anaesthesia onset is preferred. These blocks' increased duration suggests that dexmedetomidine may provide longer postoperative pain relief, improving patient comfort and possibly shortening hospital stays [9,10].

The findings align with prior research that has highlighted the advantages of using dexmedetomidine alongside regional anaesthesia [11]. The analgesic and sedative effects of dexmedetomidine are attributed to its alpha-2 adrenergic agonist properties, which do not cause significant respiratory depression [12]. This double advantage is especially beneficial in outpatient surgical settings, where the goal is to quickly recover from anaesthesia while effectively managing pain. Research conducted by Swami et al. and Gupta et al. has found that dexmedetomidine can improve block characteristics without causing any significant increase in adverse events [13,14].

Table 1: This table effectively condenses the study results, making it easy to compare the effects of the addition of dexmedetomidine to levobupivacaine on various parameters of brachial plexus block efficacy and safety

Outcome	Control Group (Levobupivacaine)	Experimental Group (Dexmedetomidine-Levobupivacaine)	p-value
Onset of Sensory Block (min)	18.7 ± 2.8	12.5 ± 2.1	< 0.001
Onset of Motor Block (min)	23.4 ± 3.5	18.2 ± 3.0	< 0.001
Duration of Sensory Block (hrs)	12.7 ± 2.1	18.6 ± 2.5	< 0.001
Duration of Motor Block (hrs)	10.5 ± 1.9	16.3 ± 2.8	< 0.001
Postoperative VAS Score at 1 hr	Higher	Lower	< 0.05
Postoperative VAS Score at 2 hrs	Higher	Lower	< 0.05
Postoperative VAS Score at 4 hrs	Higher	Lower	< 0.05
Postoperative VAS Score at 12 hrs	Higher	Lower	< 0.05
Need for Rescue Analgesia	More frequent	Less frequent	< 0.01
Adverse Events	Mild (similar rates)	Mild (similar rates)	N/A

Dexmedetomidine may potentially extend the duration of a block by exerting a hyperpolarising effect on nerve cells. This effect could lead to a reduction in firing rates, ultimately enhancing the local anaesthetic effect [15]. In addition, the vasoconstrictive properties of the substance could potentially decrease the absorption of local anaesthetic from the injection site, thereby extending its local effects [16]. The findings have significant clinical implications. Through its ability to minimise the reliance on painkillers after surgery and potentially shorten the time spent in the recovery room, dexmedetomidine has the potential to greatly improve perioperative scores. These scores play a crucial role in evaluating the quality of surgical care [17].

The study's findings highlight the practicality of incorporating dexmedetomidine as an adjuvant, given its favourable safety profile. The lack of notable disparities in adverse events among the control and experimental groups supports the findings in previous studies that indicate the safety of low-dose dexmedetomidine in regional anaesthesia [18]. There are some limitations to this study. Although the study's double-blind, randomised design enhances the credibility of the findings, it is worth noting that the results may have limited applicability due to the study being conducted in a single institution. Furthermore, there is a lack of research on the potential long-term impacts of utilising dexmedetomidine in regional anaesthesia [19].

Dexmedetomidine in brachial plexus blocks and appropriate dose regimes can be studied. Further research comparing dexmedetomidine to other

adjuvants may illuminate its significance in clinical anaesthesia. Dexmedetomidine used to levobupivacaine for brachial plexus block speeds up and extends sensory and motor blocks while remaining safe. The benefits suggest that dexmedetomidine enhances upper limb surgery anaesthesia [20].

Conclusion

The addition of dexmedetomidine to levobupivacaine for brachial plexus blocks accelerates and prolongs sensory and motor blocks. These advances improve perioperative analgesia, minimise rescue analgesic use, and shorten hospital stays without increasing side effects. Our findings suggest that regional anaesthesia adjuvant dexmedetomidine may improve upper limb surgery outcomes and satisfaction. This study emphasises the necessity of dexmedetomidine in anaesthesia protocols for optimal surgical treatment and patient recovery.

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